

BRILL

JOURNAL OF EASTERN CHRISTIAN STUDIES

77 (2025) 345–377

J ECS

brill.com/jecs

“Paradise Before Paradise”: The Earliest Syriac Collections of *Apophthegmata Patrum* and the Recension of ‘Enānīšō’ (Seventh Century)

Adrian C. Pirtea | ORCID: 0000-0002-3024-9902

Austrian Academy of Sciences, Vienna, Austria

adrian.pirtea@oeaw.ac.at

Received: 7 April 2025 | Accepted: 28 September 2025 |

Published online: 2 February 2026

Abstract

Even though the Syriac collections of the lives and sayings of the Desert Fathers and Mothers, commonly known as the *Paradise*, have been accessible to scholars since the editions of Paul Bedjan (1897) and E. A. W. Budge (1904), the rich manuscript tradition of this work remains largely unstudied. The first part of this study provides a detailed description of the two problematic editions by Bedjan and Budge and a review of previous scholarship. In a second step, the essay revisits three additional direct and indirect sources that provide information about the compilation of the *Paradise* by the seventh-century monk ‘Enānīšō’: Thomas of Marga’s account in his *Book of Superiors*, Dādišō’ Qaṭrāyā’s recently edited *Commentary on the Paradise*, and the two early witnesses CPB 464 and London, British Library, Add. 17174. Through a detailed comparison of these sources, it is shown that the structure and contents of the *Paradise* varied significantly between the seventh and thirteenth century, which is why the two printed editions should be treated with caution. The final part of the essay underscores the significance of the yet unstudied sixth- and seventh-century sources of ‘Enānīšō’*s Paradise* and suggests several avenues for future research.

Keywords

Apophthegmata Patrum – Paradise of the Fathers – Syriac manuscripts – Syriac monastic hagiography – East Syriac mysticism

Published with license by Koninklijke Brill BV | DOI:10.1163/17831520-20250309

© PIRTEA, 2026 | ISSN: 1783-1555 (print) 1783-1520 (online)

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the CC BY 4.0 license.

1 Introduction

In 532 AD, the year that saw the death of the great monastic founder St. Sabbas at the *laura* he established in the Judaean Desert, an anonymous scribe at a monastery near Bostra, beyond the Jordan River, completed the earliest known Syriac collection of the lives, sayings and teachings of the Egyptian Desert Fathers and Mothers.¹ This exceptionally early codex, now kept in London (London, British Library, Add. 17176), was copied within decades of the original compilation of the *Apophthegmata Patrum* (*AP*) in fifth-century Palestine and predates the oldest extant Greek manuscripts by several centuries.² Within a short time span, this and other similar Syriac collections of *Sayings* spread across Syria and Mesopotamia, as attested by two other Syriac manuscripts copied in 534 and by a dozen other witnesses dating to the sixth and seventh centuries.³

The translation and dissemination of the *AP* introduced new ascetic models, concepts and ideals in the Syriac-speaking world and thereby fundamentally reshaped the outlook of West Syriac asceticism and monasticism. In the wake of Abraham of Kashkar's reforms in the later half of the sixth century, such "books of the Egyptian Fathers" also reached the East Syriac monastic establishment on Mt. Izla, from where they were rapidly adopted in other monastic centers of the Church of the East in the Sasanian Empire and beyond. According to a widely accepted narrative, first noted by Josephus Simonius Assemani (1687–1768) and going back to the ninth-century author Thomas of

1 Ms. London, British Library, Add. 17176; see W. Wright, *Catalogue of Syriac Manuscripts in the British Museum, Acquired since the year 1838* (London: Trustees of the British Museum, 1870–1872), vol. 3, 1072–1073. Untypically for Syriac manuscripts, the colophon on fol. 97v uses the "era of Bostra," which likely places the production of the manuscript in the vicinity of the city. On Syriac manuscripts copied in the region of Southern Syria and Jordan, see R. Hoyland, "Late Roman Provincia Arabia, Monophysite Monks and Arab Tribes: A Problem of Centre and Periphery," *Semitica et Classica* 2 (2009) 117–139, here 130.

2 On the composition of the *Apophthegmata* in fifth-century Palestine, see L. Regnault, "Les apophthegmes des Pères en Palestine aux ve-vie siècles," *Irénikon* 54 (1981) 324–335; Z. B. Smith, *Philosopher-Monks, Episcopal Authority, and the Care of the Self. The Apophthegmata Patrum in Fifth-Century Palestine* (Instrumenta Patristica et Mediaevalia 80; Turnhout: Brepols, 2017), 27–47 (with a discussion of earlier scholarship). The earliest Greek manuscripts of the *AP* date to ca. the ninth century, e.g., Athos, Monē Karakallou, ms. 251 (Diktyon 25820).

3 Ms. Sinai, St. Catherine's Monastery, Syr. 46, ms. London, British Library, Add. 12175 (both copied in 534). For a list of early Syriac manuscripts of the *AP*, see R. Draguet, *Les formes syriaques de la matière lausiaque*, 4 vols. (CSCO 389–390, 398–399, Syr. 169–170, 173–174; Leuven: Secrétariat du CorpusSCO, 1978), vol. 1, 15*. On Sinai Syr. 46, see B. Holmberg, "The Syriac Collection of *Apophthegmata Patrum* in MS Sin. Syr. 46," *Studia Patristica* 55(3) (2013) 35–57.

Marga, it was the East Syriac monk ‘Enānīšō’ from the monastery of Bēt ‘Ābē who singlehandedly reorganized the earlier apophthegmatic material into a comprehensive collection in the second half of the seventh century.⁴ This new collection, known as the *Paradise of the Fathers* (ܩܕܝܫܘܬܐ ܕܩܘܪܝܢܐ), soon superseded earlier recensions and became the standard reference, first in East Syriac, later also in West Syriac contexts, on all matters relating to early Egyptian desert monasticism.

The modern publication and translation of ‘Enānīšō’s so-called “recension of the *Paradise*” by Paul Bedjan (1897) and E. A. W. Budge (1904, 1907) further confirmed the importance of ‘Enānīšō’ and his work as a watershed moment in the Syriac reception of the *AP*. This has led not only to a scholarly overreliance on these editions for exploring the Syriac engagement with early Egyptian monastic literature, but also to the almost total neglect of those early manuscripts and recensions which *predate* ‘Enānīšō’ and for which the Belgian scholar René Draguet (1896–1980) coined the term “sources du Paradis” (MssSoPa).⁵

As part of a larger research project on the medieval reception of the *AP* in Eastern Christianity, this essay aims at reevaluating ‘Enānīšō’s role in the collection and standardization of the Syriac *AP*. In a first step, I will argue that the editions published by Bedjan and Budge represent later stages in the evolution of the *Paradise* and should not be treated uncritically as direct witnesses to ‘Enānīšō’s original work. Second, through a critical reassessment of Thomas of Marga’s account – supported by a careful comparison with other sources, including the recently edited *Commentary on the Paradise* by Dādīšō’ Qaṭrāyā and a few early manuscripts – I intend to reconstruct the formative stages of the Syriac *Paradise* in the seventh–tenth centuries, showing how they exhibit a greater redactional diversity than previously assumed. Furthermore, I will highlight the necessity to reexamine the earliest manuscripts of the “sources of the *Paradise*,” most of which remain unpublished. Finally, the essay will briefly explore two neglected elements in the *Paradise* which potentially reveal ‘Enānīšō’s original contribution (his “personal touch”) in the compilation process.⁶

4 J. S. Assemani, *Bibliotheca Orientalis Clementino-Vaticana* (Rome: Typis Sacrae Congregationis de Propaganda Fide, 1719–1728), vol. III.1, 144–146, n. 1.

5 Draguet, *Les formes syriaques*, vol. 1, 13*–14*.

6 On ‘Enānīšō’ as an author, see D. Michelson, *The Library of Paradise. A History of Contemporary Reading in the Monasteries of the Church of the East* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2022), 201–220.

2 Previous Research on the Syriac Paradise

Although a few selections of Syriac *apophthegmata* were published already in the 1850s thanks to the efforts of the Swedish scholar Otto Fredrik Tullberg (1802–1853) and his students at the University of Uppsala,⁷ the two editions of Syriac *AP* that have become standard are those published by Paul Bedjan (1838–1920) and E. A. W. Budge (1857–1934). With the exception of the Lausiatic material published by Draguet, these two editions provide the necessary starting point for any discussion of the Syriac traditions of the *Apophthegmata Patrum* and related literature (*HL, HMA*) on Fathers and Mothers of the Egyptian Desert.

While some scholars have cautioned against their reliability and their uncritical approach to the manuscript tradition, these editions are often regarded as being simply *identical* to the seventh-century recension made by ‘Enānīšō’, as described by Thomas of Marga (see Section 3). The title page of Budge’s edition suggests as much, since it explicitly identifies his edition as being “the recension of ‘Anān-Īshō’ of Bēth-‘Ābhê.”⁸ Similarly, Bedjan notes in his preface that “c’est Ananjésus [...] qui a compilé, au VII^e siècle, cette importante collection.”⁹

This attribution has never been seriously questioned, even though the name of ‘Enānīšō’ is entirely absent from the manuscript tradition of the Syriac *Paradise*. In fact, Thomas of Marga is the *only source* that mentions ‘Enānīšō’ and his editorial work. ‘Enānīšō’ is conspicuously absent from Īšō’dnaḥ’s *Book of Chastity* (ninth century), which contains short biographies of East Syriac monastic founders, including many monks linked to Bēt ‘Ābē.¹⁰ The early fourteenth-century *Catalogue of Books* by ‘Abdīšō’ of Nisibis attributes to ‘Enānīšō’ a work on lexicography, but says nothing about him compiling the *Paradise*.

7 O. F. Tullberg, *Libri qui inscribitur Paradisus Patrum partes selectae e Codicibus mss. Syriacis Musei Britannici et Bibliothecae Vaticanae excerptae notisque illustratae* (Uppsala: Reg. Acad. Typographus, 1851), which contains the theses of his students Johannes Walfridus Moberg, Johan Landin, Johan Efraim Markström, Wilhelm Ferdinand Winquist, Peter Conrad Westergård, Gustaf Christer Carlberg, and Carl Robert Lagerström.

8 E. A. W. Budge, *The Book of Paradise, being the Histories and Sayings of the Monks and Ascetics of the Egyptian Desert by Palladius, Hieronymus and others* (London: Drugulin, 1904).

9 P. Bedjan, ed., *Acta Martyrum et Sanctorum. Tomus septimus vel Paradisus Patrum* (Paris–Leipzig: Harrassowitz, 1897), vi.

10 J.-B. Chabot, “Le livre de la chasteté par Jésusdenah, évêque de Baçrah,” *Mélanges d’archéologie et d’histoire* 16(3–4) (1896) 1–80, 225–291; P. Bedjan, ed., *Liber superiorum, seu Historia Monastica, auctore Thoma, Episcopo Margensi. Liber Fundatorum Monasteriorum in regno Persarum et Arabum. Homiliae Mar-Narsetis in Joseph. Documenta Patrum de quibusdam verae fidei dogmatibus* (Paris–Leipzig: Harrassowitz, 1901), 437–517.

Elsewhere in the *Catalogue*, ‘Abdišō’ simply attributes the *Book of Paradise*, in three volumes, to Palladius and Jerome.¹¹ While we have no reason to dismiss Thomas’ account, a closer look at the two editions of Bedjan and Budge, combined with a new examination of the indirect evidence (Thomas of Marga, Dādišō’ Qaṭrāyā) and the extant manuscript witnesses, calls for a reconsideration of ‘Enānīšō’'s role as the sole author/compiler of the Syriac *Paradise of the Fathers*.

2.1 *Paul Bedjan’s Edition (1897)*

Paul Bedjan published his edition of the *Paradise of the Fathers* as the seventh and last volume of his monumental series *Acta Martyrum et Sanctorum*.¹² Bedjan’s brief preface is instructive with regard to his ecdotic methods and choices, but it also highlights the artificial and composite character of his work.

Bedjan’s edition was based primarily on the nineteenth-century manuscript Paris, Bibliothèque nationale de France, Syriaque 317, which he transcribed and collated with Berlin, Staatsbibliothek, Sachau 329 (dated 1826), as well as several London manuscripts of much earlier date (British Library, Add. 12173, Add. 17173, Add. 17177, Add. 14583, and Add. 17174).¹³ His transcription was then sent to a collaborator in Rome, who compared it against Vatican, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Sir. 126 (dated to 1223). Following this verification, Bedjan chose to adopt the structure of the Vatican manuscript for his edition, incorporating texts found in this codex but absent in Paris Syr. 317, and vice versa.¹⁴ Additionally, he included John Chrysostom’s *Encomium on the Monks of Egypt*

11 ‘Abdišō’ bar Brikha, *Catalogue*, § 75 (‘Enānīšō’), cf. § 46 (Palladius and Jerome); see now S. Stadel, *The Catalogue of Books of ‘Abdišō’ bar Brikha, Translated with an Introduction and Notes* (Eastern Christian Texts 2; Leiden: Brill, 2025), 149, 118.

12 P. Bedjan, ed., *Acta Martyrum et Sanctorum*, 7 vols. (Paris–Leipzig: Harrassowitz, 1890–1897), henceforth cited as *AMS* and the volume number (in Roman numerals). On Bedjan’s life, see H. Murre-van den Berg, “Paul Bedjan, Missionary for Life (1838–1920),” in P. Bedjan, ed., *Homilies of Mar Jacob of Sarug / Homiliae Selectae Mar-Jacobi Sarugensis*, with additional material by Sebastian P. Brock, Biography of Paul Bedjan by Heleen Murre-van den Berg (Piscataway, NJ: Gorgias Press, 2006), 340–369.

13 In addition, Bedjan noted selected variants of BL Add. 14612 and BL Add. 12174 (Bedjan, *AMS VII*, 1010–1012).

14 Bedjan, *AMS VII*, x: “Nos cahiers, copiés sur le manuscrit de Paris, et vérifiés sur l’original par nous-même, collationnés avec les manuscrits de Berlin et de Londres par nous-même, ont été envoyés ensuite à Rome pour être vérifiés sur le manuscrit de la Bib. du Vatican. C’est ce dernier que nous avons adopté quant au nombre et à l’ordre des récits et des matières; nous y avons fait copier tout ce qui ne se trouvait pas dans le manuscrit de Paris. Nous dirons cependant que nous avons conservé des récits qui se trouvent dans le parisien mais pas dans le romain, comme par exemple l’histoire d’Évagre et celle de Marcus ou Malchus [...]”

and the corpus of Abraham of Nathpar based on BL Add. 17174, even though these sections are missing in the Paris and Vatican manuscripts.¹⁵ Bedjan's edition, therefore, was compiled from a somewhat arbitrary selection of manuscripts that belong broadly to the textual tradition of the *Paradise*, but which do not necessarily share a close genealogical relationship.¹⁶ As the following table makes clear, Bedjan's printed edition is eclectic and does not correspond exactly in content or structure to any known manuscript of the Syriac *Paradise*.

TABLE 1 The Contents of Bedjan's Edition of the *Paradise* (1897)

Parts	Contents	Bedjan 1897	Manuscripts Used ¹⁷
Part I (Pa1)	<i>First Part of Palladius</i> (HL)	pp. 1–193	Par. Syr. 317, fol. 43r–105r Vat. Sir. 126, fol. 2v–39r BL Add. 12173, fol. 118r–137r BL Add. 17173 BL Add. 17177 Berlin, Sachau 329
Part II (Pa2)	<i>Second Part of Palladius</i> (HL) + other stories ¹⁸	pp. 193–329	Par. Syr. 317, fol. 105r–149v ¹⁹ Vat. Sir. 126, fol. 39r–60v BL Add. 12173 BL Add. 17173 BL Add. 17177 Berlin, Sachau 329

15 Bedjan, *AMS* VII, x: “Nous avons également copié dans le manuscrit, add. 17,174, le discours de St. Chrysostome et celui d'Abraham Naptraïa pour les ajouter en appendice à notre édition; ils ne se trouvent pas dans le manuscrit de Rome.” On these texts, see below.

16 See G. Gomiero, “The Most Ancient Manuscript Witness to the *Paradise of the Fathers* (CPB 464, *olim* Mosul 810 and Mosul Scher 94): A New Description and Some Preliminary Remarks,” *Hugoye* 27(1) (2024) 101–164, here 146–148.

17 For the London and Berlin manuscripts, it was not always possible to indicate the precise folio numbers that Bedjan used for his edition.

18 The non-Lausic parts of Pa2 are still very little studied; see now Gomiero, “The Most Ancient Witness.”

19 In this section, Bedjan was particularly selective with the texts he included in the edition. For example, he eliminated the *Life of Paul* (absent in Vat. Sir. 126, present in Par. Syr. 317), since he had already published the *Life* in *AMS* V, 561–572. He further included the *Lives of Evagrius* and *Malchus* (extant in Par. Syr. 317, missing in Vat. Sir. 126) and the *Life of Marina/Marinos*, extant in Vat. Sir. 126 and missing in Par. Syr. 317.

TABLE 1 The Contents of Bedjan’s Edition of the Paradise (1897) (*cont.*)

Parts	Contents	Bedjan 1897	Manuscripts Used ¹⁷
Part III (Pa ₃)	<i>Part of Jerome</i> (HMA)	pp. 329–442	Par. Syr. 317, fol. 149v–182v Vat. Sir. 126, fol. 60v–81r BL Add. 12173, fol. 58v–73r BL Add. 17173 BL Add. 17177 Berlin, Sachau 329
Part IV (Pa ₄)	<i>Third Part of Palladius</i> (AP)	pp. 442–889	Vat. Sir. 126, fol. 81r–161v BL Add. 17174, fol. 1v–166r BL Add. 14583, fol. 1v–61v (until p. 615) ²⁰
AbNat 4 ²¹	Abraham of Nathpar, <i>Demonstrations</i>	pp. 889–892	BL Add. 17174, fol. 174v–175v
AbNat 7	Abraham of Nathpar, <i>Exhortation</i>	pp. 892–894	BL Add. 17174, fol. 183r–184r
DQE	Dādīšō’ Qatrāyā, <i>Epitome of the Commentary on Paradise</i> ²²	pp. 895–963	Vat. Sir. 126, fol. 161v–174v
AbNat 5	Abraham of Nathpar (?), <i>Questions and Answers</i> ²³	pp. 964–978	Vat. Sir. 126, fol. 174v–177r BL Add. 17174, fol. 175v–180r

20 Bedjan, *AMS* VII, x. The manuscript BL Add. 14583 contains the complete Pa₄, but Bedjan could not extend his stay in London in order to collate the rest of the manuscript.

21 The numbering of the texts attributed to Abraham of Nathpar follows C. Chahine, “Le témoignage de Thomas de Margâ sur les extraits d’Abraham Nethprâîâ dans le Livre du Paradis de ‘Nânîšō’,” *Augustinianum* 40(2) (2000) 439–460, here 459.

22 This section also includes excerpts from Isaac of Nineveh; see N. Sims-Williams, “Dādīšō’ Qatrāyā’s Commentary on the *Paradise of the Fathers*,” *Analecta Bollandiana* 112 (1994) 33–64, here 36 n. 12, 56; D. Phillips, ed., *Dadisho’ Qatraya. Commentaire sur le Paradis des Pères*, 3 vols. (Sources chrétiennes 626–628; Paris: Cerf, 2022), vol. 1, 74–75.

23 This section is anonymous in the manuscript. Nicholas Sims-Williams identifies it as a work by John the Solitary on the basis of London, BL Add. 17170 (a. 774/5), fol. 10v–14r, where this attribution is made. In his index of John the Solitary’s works, Werner Strothmann considers this text spurious, but only because he believes it to be an extract from ‘Enānīšō’s *Paradise*; see W. Strothmann, *Johannes von Apamea* (Patristische Texte und Studien 11; Berlin–New York: De Gruyter, 1972), 38–39. Given that BL Add. 17170 is a comprehensive collection of John the Solitary’s authentic works, it is possible that this short text is also by John. On the other hand, Chahine attributes it to Abraham of Nathpar; see Chahine, “Le témoignage de Thomas de Margâ,” 460, n. 92. The authorship of this section requires further investigation.

TABLE 1 The Contents of Bedjan's Edition of the *Paradise* (1897) (*cont.*)

Parts	Contents	Bedjan 1897	Manuscripts Used ¹⁷
AbNat 6	<i>Dialogue on the Vision of the Mind</i> ²⁴	pp. 979–986	BL Add. 17174, fol. 180v–183r Vat. Sir. 126, fol. 177r–178v
JoAnt	<i>Story of John of Antioch</i>	pp. 986–989	Vat. Sir. 126, fol. 178v–179r Berlin, Sachau 329, fol. 244v–247r
JoSab	<i>Story of John the Sabaite</i> (= N.761bis) ²⁵	pp. 989–991	Vat. Sir. 126, fol. 179r Berlin, Sachau 329, fol. 247r–248v
JoChr	John Chrysostom, <i>Praise of the Monks of Egypt</i> (= <i>Hom. on Matthew 8</i>)	pp. 992–1001	BL Add. 17174, fol. 166r–170r
AbNat 1	Abraham of Nathpar, <i>Treatise</i>	pp. 1001–1010	BL Add. 17174, fol. 170v–174v

Obviously, Bedjan's aim was never to create a critical edition of the *Paradise*, but rather to provide a comprehensive collection of all the apophthegmatic material available in Syriac. In this sense, his choice of the Vatican manuscript, the only one to contain all four parts (Pa1–Pa4), is understandable. While the structure of Bedjan's edition generally reflects the basic structure of 'Enānīšō's recension (as described by Thomas), the two are not identical, as Bedjan himself concedes. For example, the number of *apophthegmata* in Thomas' account differs from the number found in the manuscripts used by Bedjan.²⁶ More-

24 Chahine considers this text to be by Abraham of Nathpar ("Le témoignage de Thomas de Margâ", 455–457); see also Michelson, *The Library of Paradise*, 215–216. However, the *Dialogue* is, in fact, a translation of a short Greek text titled Περὶ τοῦ πῶς δεῖ καθίσαι ἐν τῷ κελίῳ καὶ περὶ θεωρίας, κατ' ἐρώτησιν καὶ ἀπόκρισιν (ca. sixth century), which is sometimes appended to Greek collections of *apophthegmata*. See J.-C. Guy, "Un entretien monastique sur la contemplation," *Recherches de science religieuse* 50/2 (1962) 230–241, who also notes the existence of the Syriac version included in the *Paradise*.

25 The Berlin manuscript reads **ⲁⲛⲟⲩ**, but this must be a corruption of Gr. Σαβᾶίτης (the Vatican manuscript attributes the story to "one of the Fathers"). This story is attested in Anastasius of Sinai and the Armenian *AP*. For the Greek text, see J. Wortley, *The Anonymous Sayings of the Desert Fathers. A Select Edition and Complete English Translation* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013), 622. Its protagonist, "the wondrous John" (ὁ θαυμάσιος Ἰωάννης) is a contemporary of the Sasanian sack of Jerusalem in 614, as we learn from another story (*ibid.*, 620–623, see N.761, *BHG* 1448w). This text must be a later addition to the *Paradise*.

26 Bedjan, *AMS* VII, viii–ix.

over, the order of the texts in Bedjan’s edition does not always match the order found in the manuscripts, and some texts found in the manuscripts are simply omitted in his edition. Finally, the epitome of Dādīšō’s *Commentary on the Paradise* is clearly a later addition, not attested in manuscripts of the *Paradise* before the thirteenth century.²⁷

2.2 *The Edition and Translations by E. A. W. Budge (1904, 1907)*

The prolific British scholar of the ancient and medieval Near East Ernest Alfred Wallis Budge (1857–1934) published his edition and translation of the Syriac *Paradise* in 1904. His English translation, revised and reissued in 1907 and 1934, remains the only complete modern rendering of the *Paradise*.²⁸ While Budge’s edition largely overlaps with that of Bedjan, the two scholars employed different editorial approaches, resulting in some key variations between their texts.

Budge’s first discussion of ‘Enānīšō’s *Paradise* can be found in his edition and translation of Thomas of Marga’s *Book of Governors*, where he provides a long explanatory note on the Syriac *Paradise* following Thomas’ chapter on ‘Enānīšō’.²⁹ Here, Budge recounts how in 1888 the vicar of the Chaldean Patriarch (possibly Jacques-Michel Naamo, d. 1895) showed him an “old and complete” copy of the “Lives of Holy Men” by Palladius. Observing that the text was “different” from the versions known to him, Budge asked for a copy by a professional scribe to be made. Budge also adds that his “investigations and enquiries in and around Mosul proved that this version was believed to be the redaction [...] made by ‘Ānān-Īshō’ at the request of George the Patriarch.”³⁰ Budge then proceeds with a description of the manuscript copy produced for him (copied by ‘Īsā bar Eš‘ayā in the village of Alqosh in 1890). As Budge notes,

27 Phillips, *Dadisho’ Qatraya. Commentaire*, vol. 1, 73–75.

28 Budge, *The Book of Paradise* (1904 edition); E. A. W. Budge, *The Paradise or Garden of the Holy Fathers, Being Histories of the Anchorites, Recluses, Monks, Coenobites, and Ascetic Fathers of the Deserts of Egypt between A.D. CCL and A.D. CCCC circiter*, 2 vols. (London: Chatto & Windus, 1907); E. A. W. Budge, *Stories of the Holy Fathers, Being Histories of the Anchorites, Recluses, Monks, Coenobites and Ascetic Fathers of the Deserts of Egypt, between A.D. 250 and A.D. 400 circiter* (London: Oxford University Press–H. Milford, 1934); E. A. W. Budge, *The Wit and Wisdom of the Christian Fathers of Egypt: The Syriac Version of the Apophthegmata Patrum by ‘Ānān Īshō’ of Bêth ‘Ābhê* (London: Oxford University Press–H. Milford, 1934).

29 E. A. W. Budge, *The Book of Governors: The Historia Monastica of Thomas, Bishop of Margā A.D. 840, Edited from Syriac Manuscripts in the British Museum and Other Libraries*, 2 vols. (London: K. Paul Trench Trubner & Co., 1893), vol. 2, 192–206.

30 *Ibid.*, 193.

the manuscript follows a similar structure in four parts similar to the *Paradise* in Vat. Sir. 126.³¹

In the introduction to his 1904 edition, Budge expands on the history of the Mosul manuscript, offering additional details about its lacunae and possible dating (ca. thirteenth–fourteenth century). He also notes that his copy of the Mosul codex was later gifted to Lady Meux (Valerie Susan Meux, née Langdon, 1852–1910), who had sponsored the publication of the edition and translation.³² Budge highlights several structural differences between the Lady Meux manuscript and Thomas' description, including discrepancies in the number of chapters and the presence of Athanasius' *Life of Antony* at the beginning of the work. Although Budge acknowledges consulting additional Syriac manuscripts in the British Library, he makes no attempt to situate the version he published within the broader textual tradition of the *Paradise*.³³ Notably, Budge also incorporated several texts from Bedjan's edition in his translation, even though they were absent from the Lady Meux manuscript (see Table 2). Both the Mosul manuscript and its copy are now considered lost, which makes Budge's 1904 edition a valuable direct witness to the Syriac *Paradise*.

TABLE 2 Contents of Budge's Edition (1904) and Translation (1904/1907) of the *Paradise*

Parts	Contents	Budge's Edition, 1904 (ms. Lady Meux 6)	Budge's Translation (1904/1907)
VA	Athanasius, <i>Life of Antony</i>	pp. 3–92 (fol. 1r–40v)	pp. 3–108 / I.3–76
Part I (Pa1)	<i>First Part of Palladius</i>	pp. 93–242 (fol. 41r–108v)	pp. 111–299 / I.77–196
Part II (Pa2)	<i>Second Part of Palladius</i>	pp. 242–345 (fol. 108v–156v)	pp. 300–482 / I.197–316
Part III (Pa3)	<i>Part of Jerome</i>	pp. 345–431 (fol. 156v–197r)	pp. 485–585 / I.317–382
Part IV (Pa4)	<i>Third Part of Palladius</i>	pp. 432–725 (fol. 197r–333r)	pp. 589–941 / II.3–242

31 Ibid.

32 Budge, *Book of Paradise* (1904), lvii–lxxviii.

33 Ibid., lxiii–lxv, lxxv–lxxvii. As Giovanni Gomiero informs me, the lost Mosul copy may be identical with ms. Mossoul 809 (olim Scher 95), which has now resurfaced among Draguet's microfilms in Louvain-la-Neuve. See below, n. 79. If this is the case, then the model of the Lady Meux manuscript cannot be as ancient as Budge claimed. The matter needs further investigation.

TABLE 2 Contents of Budge's Edition (1904) and Translation (1904/1907) of the *Paradise* (cont.)

Parts	Contents	Budge's Edition, 1904 (ms. Lady Meux 6)	Budge's Translation (1904/1907)
Pa4-Add.	Additional Chapters	– (from Bedjan)	pp. 941–967 / II.242–260
AbNat 4	Abraham of Nathpar, <i>Demonstrations</i>	pp. 725–727 (fol. 333r–334r)	pp. 967–970 / II.261–262
AbNat 5	Abraham of Nathpar (?), <i>Questions and Answers</i>	pp. 727–738 (fol. 334r–338v)	pp. 970–982 / II.262–271
AbNat 6	<i>Dialogue on the Vision of the Mind</i>	pp. 738–743 (fol. 338v–341r)	pp. 982–988 / II.271–275
***	<i>Treatises of the Fathers</i>	pp. 743–751 (fol. 341r–345r)	– (doublets)
***	<i>Questions and Answers</i>	pp. 751–754 (fol. 345r–346r)	– (doublets)
***	<i>On Humility</i>	pp. 754–757 (fol. 346r–348r)	– (doublets)
Exhort ³⁴	<i>Exhortation of the Fathers</i>	pp. 757–760 (fol. 348r– 349r)	pp. 991–994 / II.277–279
AbNat 8 ³⁵	<i>Another Exhortation</i>	pp. 760–762 (fol. 349r–350r)	pp. 994–996 / II.279–280
MarJo ³⁶	<i>Exhortation of Mar Iwannis</i>	pp. 762–766 (fol. 350r–351v)	pp. 996–1000 / II.280–283
JoAnt	<i>John of Antioch</i>	– (from Bedjan)	pp. 988–991 / II.275–277
DQE	Dādišō' Qatrāyā, <i>Epitome of the Commentary on Paradise</i>	– (from Bedjan)	pp. 1001–1075 / II.283–336

2.3 Further Research on the *Paradise*: Butler (1898), Bousset (1923), Draguet (1973)

In the same years in which Budge and Bedjan were preparing their editions of the *Paradise*, the Irish Benedictine scholar Cuthbert Butler (1858–1934) pub-

34 I was not able to identify this text.

35 See Chahine, “Le témoignage de Thomas de Margâ,” 458–459.

36 I was not able to identify this text. The text cites from Evagrius and John “the Seer of the Thebaid” (of Lycopolis).

lished a critical edition of Palladius' *Historia Lausiaca* in two volumes.³⁷ The first volume consists of a long introduction which explores, *inter alia*, the manuscript tradition of the *HL* in Greek, Latin, Syriac, Armenian, Coptic, Arabic, and Ethiopic. Butler's section on the Syriac versions is the first one to take into account the early sixth- and seventh-century manuscripts which contain the *HL*, *HMA*, and *AP*.³⁸ After a comparison of Budge's manuscript ("b") and Vat. Sir. 126 ("v"), Butler rightly concludes that "it remains a matter of doubt how far the archetype of v and b faithfully represents Anan-Isho's collection; for our MSS. are all late."³⁹ Butler also draws attention to the manuscript London, British Library, Add. 17174, as it contains "Anan-Isho's rearrangement of the Apophthegmata, almost in its original form" (emphasis mine).⁴⁰ These important, but largely overlooked observations already anticipate some of the results put forward in the present study.

Another detailed analysis of the apophthegmatic sections of the *Paradise* is found in Wilhelm Bousset's *Apophthegmata. Studien zur Geschichte des ältesten Mönchtums*, published posthumously in 1923. Bousset's work is important in several respects: First, he was the first to provide a detailed comparison of the two editions by Bedjan and Budge and examine the differences between them.⁴¹ Secondly, Bousset made one of the first attempts to situate the Syriac tradition within the broader textual history of the *Apophthegmata Patrum*. By taking into account various Greek, Latin, and Armenian versions, he was able to identify, for example, intriguing parallels between the Syriac *Paradise*, the Armenian Recension A, and the smaller Latin collections of Paschasius of Dumio and Martin of Braga, compiled in the Suebi Kingdom of Galicia in the late sixth century.⁴² Finally, like Butler before him, Bousset rightly highlighted the importance of the *old recensions* of the Syriac *AP*, extant in several sixth-century manuscripts, even if he could not analyze these witnesses in detail.⁴³

37 C. Butler, *The Lausiaca History of Palladius. A Critical Discussion together with Notes on Early Egyptian Monasticism* (Cambridge: University Press, 1898); C. Butler, *The Lausiaca History of Palladius. II. The Greek Text edited with Introduction and Notes* (Cambridge: University Press, 1904).

38 Butler, *The Lausiaca History. A Critical Discussion*, 77–96. On the *HMA*, see *ibid.*, 257–277.

39 *Ibid.*, 82–83.

40 *Ibid.*, 92.

41 W. Bousset, *Apophthegmata. Studien zur Geschichte des ältesten Mönchtums*, aus dem Nachlaß herausgegeben von Theodor Hermann und Gustav Krüger (Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 1923), 26–28, 150.

42 *Ibid.*, 21–25, 31–53.

43 *Ibid.*, 29–31.

Cuthbert Butler’s valuable, but preliminary work on the Syriac *Historia Lausiaca* was taken up by René Draguet (1896–1980), who provided the most extensive discussion of the Syriac manuscript tradition on the *Paradise* to date, as well as the only critical edition of the Lausiatic material therein.⁴⁴ Draguet consulted a large number of manuscripts, which he divided into two large groups: *sources du Paradis* (MssSoPa) and *manuscrits du Paradis* (MssPa). The criterion for doing so was the discernible structural difference between these two types: MssPa reflect the standard four-part structure (Pa1–Pa4) found in Thomas of Marga’s description and the manuscripts used by Bedjan and Budge.⁴⁵ The former group, consisting of very early manuscripts of the sixth–seventh centuries, exhibit a greater variety.⁴⁶ Draguet’s work on the manuscript tradition of ‘Enānīšō’s *Paradise* also led to the discovery of ms. Mosul 810 (*olim* Scher 94, currently CPB 464), the earliest known manuscript of this work, dating to the late eighth century.⁴⁷

Since Draguet’s interest was mainly focused in the Syriac versions of the *HL*, he only examined the Lausiatic material in Pa1–Pa3 and excluded Pa4 from his analysis. Based on his extensive comparative work, Draguet was able to show that, while the overall structure of Pa1–Pa3 remained fairly stable between the ninth and the nineteenth centuries, a considerable number of omissions, additions, and rearrangements of individual texts can be discerned in the manuscripts.

To sum up this brief survey of previous scholarship, the uncritical editions published by Bedjan and Budge, based on late manuscripts, raise legitimate concerns – first noted by Cuthbert Butler – about their accuracy in reflecting ‘Enānīšō’s original seventh-century collection. A fresh examination of the manuscript tradition is therefore necessary, particularly for the non-Lausiatic sections that Draguet did not consider in his publications. Moreover, while the connection between Thomas of Marga’s description and the extant manuscripts of the Syriac *Paradise* is undeniable, a closer reading of Thomas’ account alongside other sources reveals significant variations in how the material was structured in the early period (ca. seventh–tenth centuries). This leads to a broader question regarding ‘Enānīšō’s role: How exactly did he “compile” the *Paradise*? Was his recension truly an entirely “new” creation, as Thomas suggests, or did similar collections already circulate in his time? Finally, what

44 Draguet, *Les formes syriaques*.

45 *Ibid.*, vol. 1, 44*–113*.

46 *Ibid.*, 21*–44*.

47 *Ibid.*, 47*–63*, 83*–93*. On this manuscript, see Gomiero, “The Most Ancient Witness,” and below.

is the relationship between the so-called sixth- and seventh-century “sources of the Paradise” and ‘Enānīšō’s own version? The following sections offer a preliminary exploration of these questions, which will hopefully encourage future work towards a critical edition of both ‘Enānīšō’s *Paradise* and the pre-‘Enānīšō’ recensions.

3 Thomas of Marga’s Account of ‘Enānīšō’

Thomas of Marga’s *Book of Superiors* (*Ktābā d-rēšānē*, henceforth *KdR*) is a lengthy history of the East Syriac monastery of Bēt ‘Ābē (situated northwest of ‘Aqra, northern Iraq), its abbots and its most prominent ascetics from the monastery’s foundation until Thomas’ time in the mid-ninth century. The *Book of Superiors* has been rightly praised as an exceptional source not only for local history, but also for the history of East Syriac monasticism and ascetic theology more broadly. Although the text has been edited twice, it is only recently that Thomas’ work has begun to attract the attention it deserves.⁴⁸ Since Thomas’s two chapters about ‘Enānīšō’ and his compilatory work (*KdR* 11,11 and 11,15) have steered virtually all scholarly discussions on the Syriac *Paradise* since Assemani, it will be worth having a closer look at his account.

The figure of ‘Enānīšō’ is introduced for the first time in *KdR* 11,11, after several chapters dealing with the activity of *catholicos* Išō’yahb III (sed. 649–659). ‘Enānīšō’ and his brother Išō’yahb (later bishop of Shennā, not to be confused with the *catholicos*) were students at the School of Nisibis before entering in the Great Monastery on Mt. Izla. Wishing to emulate the desert fathers, ‘Enānīšō travelled via Jerusalem to Sketis, where he “learned concerning the manner of the lives of the ascetic fathers, whose histories and questions are written in books [...],” a statement that already alludes to his later role as the “compiler” (*mṭakksānā*) of the *Paradise*.⁴⁹ Thomas then lists ‘Enānīšō’s achievements, first and foremost his “ordering of the book of canons” together with *catholicos*

48 The two editions are: Budge, *The Book of Governors* (cited above), and P. Bedjan, *Liber superiorum, seu Historia Monastica* (cited above). Thomas of Marga’s work is now the subject of a new PhD research project by Giovanni Gomiero at the University of Ghent (“Thomas of Marga and the *Book of Superiors*: Texts, Formation and Socio-Cultural Context of an East-Syrian Bishop in the Mid-Ninth Century”). See now Giovanni Gomiero, “Riflessioni ed esperimenti di metodo storiografico nelle opere di Tommaso di Marga. Annotazioni sull’utilizzo e sulla traduzione del termine *šarba*,” *Annali di scienze religiose* 17 (2024) 369–423.

49 Thomas of Marga, *KdR* 11, 11, Budge, *Book of Governors*, vol. 1, 78 (ed.), vol. 2, 175 (trans.).

Išō'yahb, i.e., the revision of the East Syriac service book, the *Hudrā*.⁵⁰ In addition, 'Enānīšō' is said to have written a letter on the “divisions of philosophy” to his brother, as well a treatise on lexicography. Thomas concludes the chapter by noting that he saw and perused 'Enānīšō's own books in the library of Bēt 'Ābē.⁵¹ Thomas refers again to these books in chapter 11.30, where we learn that the personal library of 'Enānīšō' and his brother were gifted to the monastery by his nephew Yuḥannān, who had inherited 'Enānīšō's cell and later became metropolitan of Adiabene.⁵² According to his own account, then, Thomas had access to the original manuscripts collected and copied by 'Enānīšō'.

In the context of discussing the activities of catholicos Gewargis I (sed. 659/60–680/1), Thomas returns to 'Enānīšō' at the end of chapter 11.14, where we learn that after his return from the synod of Bēt Qaṭrāyē (676), Gewargis commissioned 'Enānīšō' with compiling the stories and sayings of the Fathers:

ܟܬܝܒܐ ܕܗܘܬܝܚܘܠܝܐ : ܕܥܣܘܒܐ ܟܘܢ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ
 ܕܥܘܠܡܐ : ܟܘܢ ܕܗܘܬܝܚܘܠܝܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ : ܟܘܢ
 ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ
 ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ
 ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ

And he entreated the wise and holy father 'Enānīšō' that he would collect the chapters and questions which were scattered about in a confused manner and were sown mixedly through the various sections of the [Book] of the histories, and narratives, and triumphs, and the questions and answers of the solitary fathers – now this book was called the “Sayings of the Elders” – and that he would make each question follow that to which it belonged in consecutive order.⁵³

In the next chapter (*KdR* 11.15), Thomas goes on to describe in detail 'Enānīšō's composition of the *Paradise* at the request of catholicos Gewargis, an activity that Thomas deliberately compares to 'Enānīšō's earlier arrangement of the *Hudrā* under catholicos Išō'yahb III:

50 Thomas of Marga, *KdR* 11, 11, Budge, *Book of Governors*, vol. 1, 79 (ed.), vol. 2, 176–177 (trans.).
 51 Thomas of Marga, *KdR* 11, 11, Budge, *Book of Governors*, vol. 1, 80 (ed.), vol. 2, 178–179 (trans.).
 52 Thomas of Marga, *KdR* 11, 30, Budge, *Book of Governors*, vol. 1, 105–106 (ed.), vol. 2, 236 (trans.).
 53 Thomas of Marga, *KdR* 11.14, Budge, *Book of Governors*, vol. 1, 86 (ed.), vol. 2, 188–189 (trans., modified).

ܕܗܘܘܢ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܩܕܝܫܐ : ܕܗܘܘܢ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܩܕܝܫܐ . ܕܗܘܘܢ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܩܕܝܫܐ
 ܕܗܘܘܢ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܩܕܝܫܐ . ܕܗܘܘܢ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܩܕܝܫܐ : ܕܗܘܘܢ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܩܕܝܫܐ
 : ܕܗܘܘܢ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܩܕܝܫܐ . ܕܗܘܘܢ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܩܕܝܫܐ : ܕܗܘܘܢ ܕܥܘܠܡܐ ܕܩܕܝܫܐ

[‘Enānīšō‘ also compiled] four hundred and thirty other chapters, which treat generally of all kinds of virtue, and many others to which he did not affix numbers nor did he arrange them in order. And he took from the Commentary on blessed Matthew the Evangelist, the discourse which was composed by Mar John Chrysostom on the praises of the Egyptian solitaries, and the questions, demonstrations and treatises of blessed Abraham of Nathpar, which he himself (‘Enānīšō‘) collected from the writings of the Fathers. And he arranged the whole work in two volumes; in the first part were the histories of the holy Fathers composed by Palladius and Jerome, and in the second part were the questions and narratives of the fathers which he himself had collected. And he called this book “Paradise,” and thus it is handed down and received in all the monasteries of the East, and the fathers everywhere praise his intelligence and applaud his work.⁵⁸

Here again, Budge apparently misunderstood certain points in Thomas’ description, which Charbel Chahine later corrected, by pointing out that the sequence “questions, demonstrations, and treatises” must all refer to various works by Abraham of Nathpar which ‘Enānīšō‘ included at the end of the work.⁵⁹ It is also worth noting that Thomas attributes to ‘Enānīšō‘ the new title for the entire compilation, i.e., *the Book of Paradise*, whereas the collection was previously called simply “The Sayings of the Elders.” Thus, according to Thomas’ description, the *Paradise* of ‘Enānīšō‘ consisted of the following parts:

58 Thomas of Marga, *BG* 11.15, Budge, *Book of Governors*, vol. 1, 87–88 (ed.), vol. 2, 190–192 (trans., modified).
 59 Chahine, “Le témoignage de Thomas de Margâ,” 446–449. Budge (*Book of Governors*, vol. 2, 191) had translated the passage as follows: “and the Questions of the blessed Mâr Abraham of Nephthar (sic!), and other examples and narratives which he himself had collected,” which implies that only the “Questions” were the work of Abraham.

TABLE 3 The Structure of the *Paradise* according to Thomas of Marga

Book of Paradise	Contents as described by Thomas of Marga
Part/Volume I (<i>palgūtā/mnātā qadmāyā</i>)	i. Histories of Palladius (Pa1–Pa2) ii. Histories of Jerome (Pa3)
Part II (<i>palgūtā/mnātā d- tartēn</i>)	i. Fourteen Sections, with 615 sayings ii. Another section with 430 sayings iii. Other chapters (with no number or order) iv. John Chrysostom's <i>Encomium on the Monks of Egypt</i> v. The Questions (<i>šūālē</i>), Demonstrations (<i>taḥwyātā</i>) and Treatises (<i>šarbē</i>) of Abraham of Nathpar

Thomas briefly refers to the *Paradise* again in *KdR* v, 15, where he recounts a discussion on the manner in which the *Book of Paradise* was originally composed in Greek. Palladius is duly credited with the composition of the “histories of the holy Fathers” and with collecting the Fathers’ sayings and counsels (i.e., the *apophthegmata*).⁶⁰ Rather surprisingly, ‘Enānīšō’ is not mentioned.

Although Thomas’ detailed description clearly refers to a specific recension of the *Paradise* in use at Bēt ‘Ābē Monastery, a few questions about his account can legitimately be raised: (a) Does the above description concern the original seventh-century compilation of ‘Enānīšō’, or rather a ninth-century, possibly extended version that Thomas was acquainted with? (b) Was ‘Enānīšō’s *Paradise* as authoritative and widespread across the Church of the East as Thomas claims, or were there several competing recensions of the *Paradise* in circulation?⁶¹ To this one may add (c) the vexing question regarding ‘Enānīšō’s complete “invisibility” in the manuscript tradition. These questions can be addressed, at least partially, through a comparison of Thomas’ account with the late seventh-century *Commentary on the Paradise* by Dādīšō’ Qaṭrāyā and the earliest manuscript witnesses of the *Paradise*.

60 Thomas of Marga, *BG* 11.15, Budge, *Book of Governors*, vol. 1, 308–309 (ed.), vol. 2, 547–548 (trans.).

61 These issues have already been raised by previous scholars, but mostly only tangentially. See Draguet, *Les formes syriaques*, 63*; Phillips, *Dadisho’ Qatraya. Commentaire*, vol. 1, 15–19; Gomiero, “The Most Ancient Witness,” 152–155.

But one should know that in the first book, which is called the “Volume of the Elders” (*penqītā d-sābē*), before this book was composed (*qdām d-nettakkas*) and before it was called “Paradise,” the story and exploits of St. Paul, the first hermit and first-born anchorite, was placed at the beginning [of Pa₃, i.e., instead of the Vita of John of Lycopolis].⁶⁵

Although he avoids mentioning any names, Dādišō’s remarks about the composition and renaming of the book distinctly recall Thomas’ account cited above, according to which ‘Enānīšō’ composed/ordered (*takkes*) the sayings of the Desert Fathers and named the new collection ‘Paradise’. There are, in fact, several similar questions throughout the DQC, where Dādišō’ is asked to clarify various structural features of the *Paradise of the Fathers*.⁶⁶ This is probably not a coincidence. If, as the passage above suggests, the new recension of the *Sayings* differed structurally from the ancient recensions (presumably fifth–sixth-century copies still in circulation), this innovation would have likely sparked debates and questions in the East Syriac monastic communities who were the primary audience for these collections. The questions regarding the authorship of specific texts or their specific place within the *Paradise* seem to imply that the monks were unfamiliar with the new recension at their disposal.

Dādišō’s detailed answers to these questions, as well as other elements of the DQC, allow for a comparison between the structure of the *Paradise* that Dādišō’ used (= PaDQ), ‘Enānīšō’’s redaction as described by Thomas of Marga (= PaTM), and the extant manuscripts of the *Paradise* (= MssPa) studied by Draguet and used by Bedjan and Budge in their editions.

On a macrostructural level, all three versions (PaDQ, PaTM, MssPa) clearly attest to the same type of collection. To begin with, they are all divided into two main parts (*palgwātā*): Part One, which consists of the two books of Palladius (Pa₁–2) and the book of Jerome (Pa₃), and Part Two, consisting of thematic series of *apophthegmata* (Pa₄). In the DQC, this division is indicated both by the titles for each part and by the introduction to DQC 11, where the brothers mention “the first three parts, i.e., the histories of the Exploits of the Solitary Fathers written by the excellent Palladius,” and “the other part of Palladius, i.e., the questions of the brothers and the teachings of the elders.”⁶⁷ Furthermore, PaDQ agrees with PaTM in dividing the *apophthegmata* in Part 11 in *fifteen* sections. While Thomas does not provide any specific titles for these sections, the

65 Dādišō’, *DQC I*.66, ed. Phillips, vol. 1, 354–357.

66 See e.g., Dādišō’, *DQC I*.101–105, ed. Phillips, vol. 1, 458–467.

67 Dādišō’, *DQC II*, Prologue, ed. Phillips, vol. 2, 8–9.

titles in Dādišō’s *Commentary* and the manuscripts agree almost *verbatim*.⁶⁸ Another remarkable point of convergence is the total number of narratives attributed to Palladius and Jerome. In DQC 1.101, Dādišō’ attributes a total of 110 stories to Palladius included in Pa1–Pa2, and 31 stories to Jerome (mainly in Pa3, but also Pa2). Almost identical numbers can be found in the earliest manuscript CPB 464 and the table of contents dated to 794 AD in the same manuscript.⁶⁹ These structural similarities leave no doubt that PaDQ, PaTM and MssPa are to be distinguished from the earlier Syriac recensions of the *HL*, *HMA* and *AP* (Draguet’s MssSoPa), which are organized differently. However, there are also some notable differences between the *Paradise* known to Dādišō’, Thomas’ account, and the extant manuscript evidence.

A first major difference concerns the inclusion of certain longer narratives in Pa1 and Pa2. In DQC 1.102, the brothers ask Dādišō’ how many stories in Pa1 were not composed by Palladius. Dādišō’ lists six: the *Life of Antony* by Athanasius (CPG 2101, BHSE 353), the *Life of Ephrem* (BHSE 315), the *Life of Abraham Qidunāyā* (BHO 16–17, BHSE 396), the *Life of Paul the Bishop (of Qentos) and John of Edessa* (BHSE 1127), the *Life of the Man of God* (BHO 36–42, BHSE 1065), and the *Life of Pelagia* (BHO 919, BHSE 400).⁷⁰ These are all longer narratives either composed in or translated into Syriac, some of which are extant in manuscripts of the fifth–sixth centuries.⁷¹ The DQC is explicit about the inclusion of these texts in the “recent” edition of the *Paradise*. Yet, with the exception of the *Life of Antony*,⁷² these narratives are not attested in any extant manuscript of the *Paradise*. They are also absent in CPB 464 and its table of contents

68 One can compare the titles in Bedjan’s edition (*AMS* VII, 442, 479, 489, 495, 504, 525, 532, 615, 655, 670, 679, 688) with those in the *DQC* (ed. Phillips, vol. 2, 12, 144, 192, 208, 222, 224, 252, 266, 394, 516, vol. 3, 8, 48, 86).

69 If we disregard the prologues/epilogues and those texts in Pa1–Pa3 that, according to Dādišō’, are *not* by Palladius and Jerome, we get 31 stories for Jerome in both PaDQ and MssPa, and either 110 (PaDQ) or 111 (CPB 464) for Palladius.

70 Dādišō’, *DQC* 1.102, ed. Phillips, vol. 1, 458–459.

71 For the *Life of Antony*, see London, BL Add. 14646/A and London, BL Add. 14609, both of the sixth century; see S. P. Brock, *An Inventory of Syriac Texts Published from Manuscripts in the British Library* (Piscataway, NJ: Gorgias Press, 2020), 114–115, 125. For the *Life of Abraham Qidunaya* and the *Life of the Man of God*, see e.g., London, BL Add. 14644 of the fifth or sixth century (Brock, *Inventory*, 123). The *Life of Paul and John* is attested in London, BL Add. 14646/B, sixth century (Brock, *Inventory*, 125). For the *Life of Pelagia*, see London, BL Add. 14651 (a. 850), fol. 1v–23r (Brock, *Inventory*, 127) and Sinai, Syriac 30 (a. 698). See also n. 74 below.

72 In CPB 464, the *Life of Antony* is added *after the conclusion* of the *Paradise* (see below). Likewise, in the Lady Meux manuscript, published by Budge, the *Life of Antony* is placed *before* the first book of the *Paradise* as a separate text.

(Tab794). Similarly, DQC 1.104 mentions the inclusion of two *Vitae* of Serapion Sindonita in the *Paradise*, a short life at the end of Pa1, and a longer one in Pa2. While the first *Life of Serapion*, which corresponds to Palladius' *HL* 37, is indeed found in MssPa, the longer life (circulating independently since the sixth century) is not attested in any known witness to the *Paradise*.⁷³

Dādišō's version of the *Paradise* had clearly incorporated these longer hagiographic texts from earlier manuscripts. To give only one example, the sixth-century manuscript London, British Library, Add. 12160 transmits the *Lives of Abraham Qidunāyā, Paul, and John*, and the *Man of God* in almost consecutive order.⁷⁴ Since Thomas of Marga does not mention these narratives in his account, we do not know if 'Enānīšō' included them in the initial compilation (and they were later removed), or if Dādišō' had access to either a different or an expanded recension of the *Paradise*.⁷⁵ Conversely, it seems that some texts mentioned by Thomas of Marga and attested by MssPa were not included in the version of the *Paradise* used by Dādišō'. This is probably the case for John Chrysostom's *Encomium on the Monks of Egypt* and the corpus of Abraham of Nathpar, to which Dādišō' makes no reference in his *Commentary*.⁷⁶

5 The Early Manuscripts of the Paradise

In addition to Thomas' account and the information provided by Dādišō', it is necessary to take into account the earliest extant manuscripts that transmit

73 Dādišō', DQC 1.104, ed. Phillips, vol. 1, 450–461. The longer *Life of Serapion* is attested e.g., in ms. London, BL Add. 14597, copied in 569 (Brock, *Inventory*, 112), which also contains the *Life of Paul of Qentos and John*. The longer *Life of Serapion* was published by Paul Bedjan in *AMS* v, 263–341.

74 On this manuscript, see Wright, *Catalogue*, vol. 3, 1090–1091; Brock, *Inventory*, 62 (with bibliography).

75 For Pa2 and Pa3, the structure attested by DQC is more in line with the manuscript evidence. The texts mentioned in DQC 1.103 (ed. Phillips, vol. 1, 458–461) as not being written by Palladius (*Life of Paul of Thebes*, the *Long Life of Pachomius*, and the *Story of the Two Brothers who lived in Persia*) are usually found in the manuscripts. Note, however, the special case of the *Lives of Martinianus, Eupraxia and Onesima*, on which see Gomiero, "The Most Ancient Witness," 150–151.

76 This is admittedly an *argumentum e silentio*. However, in light of Dādišō's interests in "Patristic philology" and textual matters more generally, one would expect at least some comments on the inclusion of these two peculiar Patristic "appendices." On Dādišō's philological interests, see also A. C. Pirtea, "The Development of the Syriac *Corpus Macarianum* and the Memory of the Two *Macarii* in East Syriac Monastic Literature (Seventh–Eighth Century)," in *The Greek Sources of East Syriac Mysticism* (ed. V. Duca & J. Verheyden; Leiden: Brill, forthcoming).

‘Enānīšō’s *Paradise*. For the purposes of this study, I will restrict myself to two early manuscripts, which together constitute a “complete copy” (i.e., containing Pa1–Pa4) of the *Paradise*: Baghdad, Chaldean Patriarchate, CPB 464 (olim Mosul 810 and Mosul, Scher 94, now relocated to the *Centre de numérisation des manuscrits orientaux/CNMO*, Ankawa, Erbil), and London, British Library, Add. 17174, copied in the year 929. These manuscripts were either unknown or only partially consulted in previous scholarship. I will occasionally refer to Bedjan’s main witness Vatican, BAV, Vat. Sir. 126 (a. 1223) and the ascetic collection Enhil, CET 76 (olim Mor Gabriel 10, a. 1207/8), the two oldest extant manuscripts to contain all four parts.⁷⁷

CPB 464 is a significantly damaged parchment codex (ca. 24 × 16.5 cm.) dated to the late eighth or early ninth century, with some parts on paper restored in the twelfth/thirteenth century. The importance of CPB 464 for the history of ‘Enānīšō’s *Paradise* was first recognized by René Draguet during his work on the *Historia Lausiaca*.⁷⁸ Due to its tumultuous history in the decades since, the manuscript deteriorated further and is now very fragmentary. Fortunately, the microfilm copy used by Draguet, taken when the manuscript was in a better condition, has recently resurfaced and could be taken into account by Giovanni Gomiero in his detailed analysis.⁷⁹ As briefly mentioned above, after the *Paradise* the manuscript contains a detailed table of contents with a colophon dated to 794 AD (*Tab794*), copied by the same anonymous scribe (fols. 93v–95r).⁸⁰ Since the order in *Tab794* does not always correspond to the order found in the manuscript, Draguet concluded that the table of contents did not originally belong to CPB 464, but rather to its model.⁸¹ In what follows, I will note any divergences between *Tab794* and CPB 464.

In its current state, the manuscript contains only Pa2 and Pa3, though originally it will have contained Pa1 as well. A striking difference between *Tab794* and CPB 464 is that the table of contents distinguishes between Pa1 and Pa2,

77 On these latter two manuscripts, see Draguet, *Les formes syriaques*, vol. 1, 78*–79*, 93*–96*.

78 *Ibid.*, 83*–93*.

79 Gomiero, “The Most Ancient Witness.” On Draguet’s collection of microfilms, see N. Atas, C. E. Biuzzi, G. Gomiero, & A. B. Schmidt, “Le *Paradis retrouvé* à Louvain-la-Neuve. Inventaire préliminaire des microfilms de manuscrits du Fonds René Draguet-CSCO, suivi d’un Appendice sur les manuscrits syriaques du Centre d’Études sur Grégoire de Nazianze,” *BABELAO* 13 (2024) 127–151. The manuscript is available online in the vHMML Reading Room: <https://www.vhmml.org/readingRoom/view/503258> (registration required; last accessed 2.4.2025).

80 Draguet, *Les formes syriaques*, 47*–63*.

81 Draguet, *Les formes syriaques*, 85*–88*; cf. Gomiero, “The Most Ancient Witness,” 111–112, 147–148.

while the latter presents them *together* as the “first part” of Palladius’ *Paradise* (ܩܕܝܫܐ ܩܕܝܫܐ).⁸² There is no indication that the manuscript ever contained Pa4. On the contrary, at the end of *Tab794* on fols. 93v–95r, it is stated that the volume represents the “complete Book of Paradise” (ܩܕܝܫܐ ܩܕܝܫܐ ܩܕܝܫܐ). After the table, the manuscript continues with Athanasius’ *Life of Antony*, which is clearly distinguished from the previous sections and is not mentioned in *Tab794*.⁸³ Given that CPb 464 only contained Pa1–3, does this mean that, at this stage, the fourth part compiled by ‘Enānīšō’ was not (yet) considered to be part of the *Paradise*? What is more, John Chrysostom’s *Encomium on the Monks of Egypt*, which according to Thomas was placed at the end of Pa4, is included here as the conclusion to Pa3. One possible explanation is that the two parts of ‘Enānīšō’s *Paradise* (Pa1–3 and Pa4, respectively) could also circulate as two separate volumes/tomes and were not necessarily regarded as a single, unitary work.

Although *Tab794* and CPb 464 agree for the most part with the editions of Bedjan and Budge, Gomiero rightly draws attention to several structural differences. For instance, *Tab794* and CPb 464 include the *Life of Martinianus* (BHO 699), the *Life of Eupraxia* (BHSE 1980) and the *Life of Onesima* (BHSE 359) in Pa2. The first *Vita* is also discussed in Dādīšō’s DQC, but it later disappears in the manuscript tradition of the *Paradise*, while the latter two are absent both from DQC and the later manuscripts.⁸⁴ As Gomiero concludes, the structure of the *Paradise* in *Tab794* and CPb 464 probably reflect an “intermediate stage” between the original recension of ‘Enānīšō’ and the account of Thomas of Marga.⁸⁵

The second manuscript is London, BL Add. 17174 (= L), already mentioned above. The manuscript is of West Syriac origin and was copied by a scribe from Melitene at an unknown location in 929.⁸⁶ As it contains only Pa4, this manuscript attests to the fact that the two parts of the *Paradise* could indeed circulate independently. The text of Pa4 in L served as a model for the eleventh-cen-

82 Draguet, *Les formes syriaques*, 87*; Gomiero, “The Most Ancient Witness,” 136.

83 Draguet, *Les formes syriaques*, 86*–87*; Gomiero, “The Most Ancient Witness,” 145.

84 Dādīšō, DQC I.56, ed. Phillips, vol. 1, 324–329; cf. Gomiero, “Most Ancient Witness,” 120–122, 150–151. On the *Life of Martinianus*, see G. Venturini, “La tradizione manoscritta della *Storia di Martiniano* e le sue versioni siriane,” *Le Muséon* 134(3–4) (2021) 283–323. As Gomiero notes (121–122), Elias of Nisibis (d. 1046) still read the *Life of Martinianus* as part of the *Paradise* in the eleventh century, but the *Life* is not included in any MssPa known today.

85 Gomiero, “The Most Ancient Witness,” 152–155.

86 Wright, *Catalogue*, vol. 3, 1074–1076.

ture manuscript London, BL Add. 14583. Since L lost some of its folios, the later copy helps reconstruct some of its lacunae.

As noted by Butler and Chahine, the collection in L probably remains very close to ‘Enānišō’s original compilation, despite its West Syriac provenance.⁸⁷ The manuscript contains several hundred *apophthegmata* divided across fourteen thematic chapters (fols. 1v–91r), followed by a fifteenth chapter with hundreds of other entries (fol. 91r–166r).⁸⁸ The titles of these chapters are identical to those found in Dādišō’s DQC and in the manuscripts used by Bedjan and Budge.⁸⁹ In full accordance with Thomas’ description, the last section of the manuscript includes Chrysostom’s *Encomium* (fol. 166r–170r) and the corpus of Abraham of Nathpar (fol. 170r–184r).

There are some minor differences between L and the later manuscripts. For example, at the end of Chapter 1 (“On the Flight from the World”), L and its copy contain two extra chapters with parallels in the Greek Systematic Collection which are absent from Vat. Sir. 126.⁹⁰ In Chapter 2, L omits the final chapter found in the Vatican manuscript.⁹¹ In other cases, both L and Vat. Sir. 126 contain chapters absent in the Lady Meux manuscript used by Budge.⁹² A thorough comparison of L with other witnesses will certainly reveal other variations as well.

6 Comparing PaDQ, PaTM and MssPa

It is time to draw some general conclusions on the structure of the *Paradise* based on all the data surveyed so far. If we take into account all the information provided by Thomas of Marga (PaTM), Dādišō’s Commentary (PaDQ), and the early manuscript witnesses (MssPa), the following picture emerges:

- 1) Unlike the early Syriac collections of *Sayings* and *Lives* (the so-called “sources of the *Paradise*”), PaDQ, PaTM, and MssPa (including those used by Bedjan and Budge) all share the same basic structure: the material is divided into two main parts, the first of which (Pa1–Pa3) consists of the texts attributed to Palladius and Jerome (HL, HMA, and other sources),

87 Chahine, “Le témoignage de Thomas de Marga,” 455–458.

88 Wright (*Catalogue*, 1074–1076) divides the contents of L in Part I, with 11 chapters (fol. 1v–80v) and Part II, with 10 chapters (fols. 80v–184r). However, this division is not found in the manuscript.

89 See above, n. 68.

90 London, BL Add. 17174, fol. 9r–v (mut.); London, BL Add. 14583, fols. 10v–12r.

91 London, BL Add. 17174, fol. 14r.

92 London, BL Add. 17174, fol. 17r.

while the second (Pa4) consists of series of *apophthegmata*. As the cases of mss. CPB 464 and L show, these two parts could circulate independently of one another. Moreover, CPB 464 shows that Pa1–Pa2 could also be regarded as a unity.

- 2) The most significant variations in structure are to be found in Pa1. Unlike any extant manuscript, PaDQ includes six long hagiographic narratives in Pa1. These narratives circulated in Syriac, either independently or as a group, since at least the sixth century. While Dādišō' clearly considers the *Life of Antony* to belong to Pa1, manuscripts such as CPB 464 and Lady Meux 6 transmit it as a separate work, while others omit it completely. The other five *Lives* are not attested in any known manuscript of the *Paradise*. It remains unclear if they ever belonged to 'Enānīšō's original collection and to PaTM, or if they were exclusive to the version used by Dādišō'.
- 3) Although the majority of texts in Pa2 are the same across all witnesses, here too there are notable differences. The *Life of Martinianus* is included in PaDQ and is attested in the earliest manuscript (Tab794/CPB 464), but disappears after the mid-eleventh century. The *Lives of Eupraxia* and *Onesima*, while present in Tab794 and CPB 464, are found neither in PaDQ, nor in any later witnesses. On the other hand, the long *Life of Serapion*, which Dādišō' includes in Pa2, is not attested elsewhere.
- 4) Pa3, which reflects recension R4a of the *HMA*,⁹³ appears to be the most stable part of the *Paradise*. However, some later manuscripts include additional material that is unrelated to the *HMA*. Notably, Enhil CET 0076 inserts several shorter narratives at the end of its Hieronymian section (Pa3) which are otherwise unattested in MssPa.⁹⁴
- 5) The basic structure of the multiple series of *apophthegmata* Pa4 is likewise remarkably stable. The titles of the 15 sections are nearly identical in PaDQ and MssPa. The vast majority of sayings are the same across all manuscript witnesses and recur in almost the exact same order. There are, however, minor variations, such as omissions or additions of individual sayings (e.g., in BL Add. 17174). This is not at all surprising considering the nature of such apophthegmatic collections. One aspect which remains unclear is if the "unnumbered sayings" in PaTM are the same as those included in the 15th section of PaDQ and MssPa.

93 On the Syriac recensions of the *HMA*, see P. Tóth, "Syriac Versions of the 'Historia Monachorum in Aegypto': A Preliminary Investigation on the Basis of the First Chapter," *Oriens Christianus* 94 (2010) 58–104.

94 I intend to analyze these stories in a future study.

6) The case of the two appendices (John Chrysostom and Abraham of Nathpar) is more complex. According to Thomas, these two sections were included in ‘Enānīšō’s collection from the beginning. However, they seem to be absent in PaDQ, while Tab794/CPB 464 only contains Chrysostom’s *Encomium*, unusually placed at the end of Pa3. It is thus at least conceivable that these appendices were included in the *Paradise* at a later stage, during the eighth and ninth centuries. The earliest attestation of *both* appendices is in BL Add. 17174. Later manuscripts often omit them. The following table summarizes the conclusions above.

TABLE 4 The Structure of the *Paradise* According to Various Sources

Parts	Contents (+ Additions or Special Cases)	PaDQ (7th c.)	Tab794 / CPB 464 (8th–9th c.)	PaTM (9th c.)	L (929)	Enhil 76 (1207/8)	Vat. Sir. 126 (1223)
Pa1	HL	+	+	+	–	+	+
	+ Antony	+	–	?	–	–	–
	+ Abraham Qidunāyā	+	–	?	–	–	–
	+ Ephrem	+	–	?	–	–	–
	+ Paul of Qentos and John	+	–	?	–	–	–
	+ Man of God	+	–	?	–	–	–
	+ Pelagia	+	–	?	–	–	–
Pa2	HL and miscellanea	+	+	+	–	+	+
	+ Paul the Hermit	+	+	?	–	+	+
	+ Pachomian Asketikon	+	+	?	–	+	+
	+ Serapion (long rec.)	+	–	?	–	–	–
	+ Malchus	+	+	?	–	+	+
	+ Martinianus	+	+	?	–	–	–
	+ Eupraxia	–	+	?	–	–	–
	+ Onesima	–	+	?	–	–	–
Pa3	HMA	+	+	+	–	+	+
	+ Shorter Narratives	–	–	–	–	+	–
Pa4	AP, Thematic Sections (1–14)	+	–	+(615)	+	+	+(616)
	AP, General Section (15)	+	–	+(430)	+	+	+(528)
	AP, Other chapters	?	–	+(n)	?	?	?
JoChr	John Chrysostom, <i>Encomium</i>	–	+	+	+	–	–
AbNat	Abraham of Nathpar, <i>Corpus</i>	–	–	+	+	–	–

7 An Outlook: ‘Enānīšō’ and the Pre-History of the Syriac *Paradise*

The above analysis has hopefully demonstrated that ‘Enānīšō’s *Paradise* exhibits a complex textual history, with multiple layers, which cannot be reconstructed solely on the basis of the editions published by Paul Bedjan and E. A. W. Budge. The discrepancies between the early indirect evidence (DQC, Thomas of Marga) and the extant manuscripts suggest a certain degree of variation and freedom in how individual scribes and compilers (re)structured the initial seventh-century recension of the *Paradise*, especially in the early period of its transmission (seventh–tenth centuries).

In order to study in detail the methods and strategies through which ‘Enānīšō’ identified, selected, rearranged, and revised the sources at his disposal, it will be therefore necessary to examine all the early “sources of the *Paradise*,” i.e., the Syriac manuscripts of the sixth–seventh centuries which contain the *HL*, *HMA*, *AP* and related texts. Except for Bo Holmberg’s study of Sinai Syr. 46 and the data provided by the *Monastica Dynamic Library and Research Tool*, these early collections have not been systematically investigated.⁹⁵

To mention only one striking feature of these early collections, it is noteworthy that they are already organized in “volumes” (*penqyān*) or “parts” (*palgwātā*) since the early sixth century. Although these early attempts at systematization differ from the new recension, they do prefigure ‘Enānīšō’s work in significant ways. For instance, the oldest dated manuscript BL Add. 17176 (a. 532), already mentioned above, is divided into two (anonymous) volumes with *Stories of the Egyptian Fathers*,⁹⁶ while the larger collection in BL Add. 12173 (sixth–seventh century) contains a volume of Jerome in two distinct parts, and a volume of Palladius.⁹⁷ Other collections are organized thematically and sometimes bear titles which recall the chapter headings in ‘Enānīšō’s *Paradise*.⁹⁸ The extent to which ‘Enānīšō’ was inspired by and adopted these earlier structures remains to be determined.

Going beyond ‘Enānīšō’s activity as a compiler and editor of pre-existing material in Syriac, it is also worth exploring (a) other innovative and original aspects of his work, and (b) the possible contacts with Western (Greek) textual

95 Holmberg, “The Syriac Collection.” For the *Monastica* project, see: <https://monastica.lu.se> (coordinated by Samuel Rubenson, last accessed 3.4.2025).

96 London, BL Add. 17176, fols. 2v–57v (first volume), fols. 58r–97v (second volume).

97 London, BL Add. 12173, fols. 2v–58v (first part), fols. 58v–117v (second part), with a reference to the “end of the volume” on fol. 117v; fols. 118v–181r (volume of Palladius).

98 See e.g., the series in London, BL Add. 12173, fols. 137r–179v, with a section title “On Humility.”

tention either. The two stories shared by the Syriac *Paradise* and John Moschos' *Pratum* could indicate 'Enānīšō's acquaintance with contemporary Greek collections. Although the narratives are not extant in the earliest manuscripts, one of them (*Pratum* § 189) may well belong to 'Enānīšō's original compilation.¹⁰² One argument in support of this hypothesis are the differences between the Syriac version and the Greek text, such as the different name of the informer from Ascalon (Eusebius in Greek, Joseph in Syriac) and the longer speech by the same at the end of the Syriac story.¹⁰³ One may tentatively posit an independent (oral?) transmission: 'Enānīšō' may have collected the story during his journey to the West independently of John Moschos, whose travels in the same regions occurred not long before. Whatever the precise path of transmission, the intriguing parallels between the *Paradise* and the *Pratum* leads to new questions about 'Enānīšō's knowledge and use of recent sources other than Syriac. The same journey to the Holy Land and Egypt may have exposed 'Enānīšō' to Greek and Coptic systematic collections of *apophthegmata*, which could have inspired his division into fifteen thematic chapters. Some of these titles find a close correspondent in Greek.¹⁰⁴

In any case, future research on 'Enānīšō's *Paradise* and its sources should not only entail a thorough examination of the early Syriac recensions, but should also consider his work against the wider background of the formation of apophthegmatic collections in other languages and their circulation in the Eastern Mediterranean.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank Giovanni Gomiero for his very helpful remarks on an earlier version of this paper. All remaining errors are my own. This publication is part of the research project "Reviving the Ascetic Ideal in the Eastern Mediter-

Moschos en syriaque," in *Le calame et le ciseau: colophons syriaques offerts à Françoise Briquel Chatonnet* (ed. S. Brelaud et al.; Cahiers d'études syriaques 8; Paris: Geuthner, 2021), 383–420.

102 John Moschos, *Pratum Spirituale* § 195 (PG 87/3, 3077–3080), cf. *Paradise* III.44 (ed. Bedjan, *AMS* VII, 855–857; Budge, *Book of Paradise* [1904], 941–942); *Pratum* § 189 (PG 87/3, 3068–3069), cf. *Paradise* III.152 (ed. Bedjan, *AMS* VII, 885–888; Budge, *Book of Paradise* [1904], 964–967). The two texts are found in Vat. Sir. 126, but are absent in London, BL Add. 17174. The latter story is also extant in a different, much shorter Syriac version, on which see Binggeli & Ruani, "Au-delà des flammes."

103 *Pratum* § 189, PG 87/3, 3068A (Eusebius); *Paradise* III.152, Bedjan, *AMS* VII, 885 (Abba Joseph).

104 See J.-C. Guy, *Les apophthegmes des Pères. Collection systématique* (3 vols.; Sources chrétiennes 387, 474, 498; Paris: Cerf, 1993–2005), vol. 1, 98–101.

ranean. Entangled Memories of Early Egyptian Monasticism in Medieval Syriac, Arabic, and Armenian Christianity (969–1375 CE)” (*RevIdEM*, ERC Starting Grant, 2023–2028; PI: Adrian C. Pirtea), hosted at the Austrian Academy of Sciences, Vienna. The project has received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union’s Ninth Framework Programme “Horizon Europe” (Grant agreement no. 101078631). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Bibliography

- Assemani, J. S., *Bibliotheca Orientalis Clementino-Vaticana*, 3 vols. (Rome: Typis Sacrae Congregationis de Propaganda Fide, 1719–1728).
- Atas, N., Biuzzi, C. E., Gomiero, G., & Schmidt, A. B., “Le Paradis retrouvé à Louvain-la-Neuve. Inventaire préliminaire des microfilms de manuscrits du Fonds René Draguet-CSCO, suivi d’un Appendice sur les manuscrits syriaques du Centre d’Études sur Grégoire de Nazianze,” *BABELAO* 13 (2024): 127–151.
- Bedjan, P., ed., *Acta Martyrum et Sanctorum*, 7 vols. (Paris–Leipzig: Harrassowitz, 1890–1897).
- Bedjan, P., ed., *Liber superiorum, seu Historia Monastica, auctore Thoma, Episcopo Margensi. Liber Fundatorum Monasteriorum in regno Persarum et Arabum. Homiliae Mar-Narsetis in Joseph. Documenta Patrum de quibusdam verae fidei dogmatibus* (Paris–Leipzig: Harrassowitz, 1901).
- Binggeli, A. & Ruani, F., “Au-delà des flammes: trois récits inédits du *Pré spirituel* de Jean Moschos en syriaque.” In *Le calame et le ciseau: colophons syriaques offerts à Françoise Briquel Chatonnet*, ed. S. Brelaud, J. Daccache, M. Debié, M. Farina, F. Ruani, & E. Villey, Cahiers d’études syriaques 8 (Paris: Geuthner, 2021), 383–420.
- Bousset, W., *Apophthegmata. Studien zur Geschichte des ältesten Mönchtums*, aus dem Nachlaß herausgegeben von Theodor Hermann und Gustav Krüger (Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 1923).
- Brock, S. P. *An Inventory of Syriac Texts Published from Manuscripts in the British Library* (Piscataway, NJ: Gorgias Press, 2020).
- Budge, E. A. W., ed., *The Book of Governors: The Historia Monastica of Thomas, Bishop of Margâ A.D. 840, Edited from Syriac Manuscripts in the British Museum and Other Libraries*, 2 vols. (London: K. Paul Trench Trubner & Co., 1893).
- Budge, E. A. W., ed., *The Book of Paradise, being the Histories and Sayings of the Monks and Ascetics of the Egyptian Desert by Palladius, Hieronymus and others* (London: Drugulin, 1904).

- Budge, E. A. W., ed., *The Paradise or Garden of the Holy Fathers, Being Histories of the Anchorites, Recluses, Monks, Coenobites, and Ascetic Fathers of the Deserts of Egypt between A.D. CCL and A.D. CCCC circiter*, 2 vols. (London: Chatto & Windus, 1907).
- Budge, E. A. W., ed., *Stories of the Holy Fathers, Being Histories of the Anchorites, Recluses, Monks, Coenobites and Ascetic Fathers of the Deserts of Egypt, between A.D. 250 and A.D. 400 circiter* (London: Oxford University Press—H. Milford, 1934).
- Butler, C., ed., *The Lausiac History of Palladius. A Critical Discussion together with Notes on Early Egyptian Monasticism* (Cambridge: University Press, 1898).
- Butler, C., ed., *The Lausiac History of Palladius. II. The Greek Text edited with Introduction and Notes* (Cambridge: University Press, 1904).
- Chabot, J.-B., “Le livre de la chasteté par Jésusdenah, évêque de Baçrah,” *Mélanges d'archéologie et d'histoire* 16(3–4) (1896): 1–80, 225–291.
- Chahine, C., “Le témoignage de Thomas de Margâ sur les extraits d'Abraham Nethprââ dans le Livre du Paradis de ‘Nânîšo’,” *Augustinianum* 40(2) (2000): 439–460.
- Chahine, C., “Abraham de Bet-Netpra, Discours (Mēm̄rē): Introduction, texte critique et traduction,” PhD Thesis, (Istituto Patristico Augustinianum, Rome, 2004).
- Croq, A., “Totem or Taboo? Souvenirs of Paradise in the Eastern Mediterranean, from Desert Fathers to Byzantine and Islamic Literature,” forthcoming.
- Draguet, R., ed., *Les formes syriaques de la matière lausiaque*, 4 vols., CSCO 389–390, 398–399, Syr. 169–170, 173–174 (Leuven: Secrétariat du CorpusSCO, 1978).
- Gomiero, G., “Riflessioni ed esperimenti di metodo storiografico nelle opere di Tommaso di Marga. Annotazioni sull'utilizzo e sulla traduzione del termine *šarba*,” *Annali di scienze religiose* 17 (2024): 369–423.
- Gomiero, G., “The Most Ancient Manuscript Witness to the *Paradise of the Fathers* (CPB 464, *olim* Mosul 810 and Mosul Scher 94): A New Description and Some Preliminary Remarks,” *Hugoye* 27(1) (2024): 101–164.
- Guy, J.-C., “Un entretien monastique sur la contemplation,” *Recherches de science religieuse* 50(2) (1962): 230–241.
- Guy, J.-C., ed., *Les apophthegmes des Pères. Collection systématique*, Sources chrétiennes 387, 474, 498 (Paris: Cerf, 1993–2005).
- Holmberg, B., “The Syriac Collection of *Apophthegmata Patrum* in MS Sin. Syr. 46,” *Studia Patristica* 55(3) (2013): 35–57.
- Hoyland, R., “Late Roman Provincia Arabia, Monophysite Monks and Arab Tribes: A Problem of Centre and Periphery,” *Semitica et Classica* 2 (2009): 117–139.
- Kessel, G. & Pinggéra, K., *A Bibliography of Syriac Ascetic and Mystical Literature*, Eastern Christian Studies 11 (Leuven: Peeters, 2011).
- Kozah, M., Abu-Husayn, A., & Mourad, S., eds., *Dadisho' Qatraya's Compendious Commentary on the Paradise of the Egyptian Fathers in Garshuni*, Texts from Christian Late Antiquity 43 (Piscataway, NJ: Gorgias Press, 2016).

- Jullien, F., “Rabban-Šāpūr: un monastère au rayonnement exceptionnel. La réforme d’Abraham de Kaškar dans le Bēth-Hūzāyē,” *Orientalia Christiana Periodica* 72(2) (2006): 333–348.
- Michelson, D., *The Library of Paradise: A History of Contemplative Reading in the Monasteries of the Church of the East* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2022).
- Murre-van den Berg, H., “Paul Bedjan, Missionary for Life (1838–1920).” In *Homilies of Mar Jacob of Sarug / Homiliae Selectae Mar-Jacobi Sarugensis*, ed. P. Bedjan, with additional material by Sebastian P. Brock, *Biography of Paul Bedjan by Heleen Murre-van den Berg* (Piscataway, NJ: Gorgias Press, 2006), 340–369.
- Phillips, D., ed., *Dadisho’ Qatraya. Commentaire sur le Paradis des Pères*, Sources chrétiennes 626–628 (Paris: Cerf, 2022).
- Pirtea, A. C., “The Development of the Syriac *Corpus Macarianum* and the Memory of the Two *Macarii* in East Syriac Monastic Literature (Seventh-Eighth Century).” In *The Greek Sources of East Syriac Mysticism*, ed. V. Duca & J. Verheyden (Leiden: Brill, forthcoming).
- Regnault, L., “Les apophthegmes des Pères en Palestine aux ve-vie siècles,” *Irénikon* 54 (1981): 324–335.
- Sims-Williams, N., “Dādišo’ Qatrāyā’s Commentary on the *Paradise of the Fathers*,” *Analecta Bollandiana* 112 (1994): 33–64.
- Smith, Z. B., *Philosopher-Monks, Episcopal Authority, and the Care of the Self. The Apophthegmata Patrum in Fifth-Century Palestine*, *Instrumenta Patristica et Mediaevalia* 80 (Turnhout: Brepols, 2017).
- Stadel, S., *The Catalogue of Books of ‘Abdisho’ bar Brikha, Translated with an Introduction and Notes*, *Eastern Christian Texts* 2 (Leiden: Brill, 2025).
- Strothmann, W., *Johannes von Apamea*, *Patristische Texte und Studien* 11 (Berlin–New York: De Gruyter, 1972).
- Subtelny, M., “The Tale of the Four Sages who Entered the Pardes: A Talmudic Enigma from a Persian Perspective,” *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 11(1–2) (2004): 3–58.
- Tóth, P., “Syriac Versions of the ‘Historia Monachorum in Aegypto’. A Preliminary Investigation on the Basis of the First Chapter,” *Oriens Christianus* 94 (2010): 58–104.
- Tullberg, O. F., ed., *Libri qui inscribitur Paradisus Patrum partes selectae e Codicibus MSS. Syriacis Musei Britannici et Bibliothecae Vaticanæ excerptae notisque illustratae* (Uppsala: Reg. Acad. Typographus, 1851).
- Venturini, G., “La tradizione manoscritta della *Storia di Martiniano* e le sue versioni siriane,” *Le Muséon* 134(3–4) (2021): 283–323.
- Wortley, J., ed., *The Anonymous Sayings of the Desert Fathers. A Select Edition and Complete English Translation* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013).
- Wright, W., *Catalogue of Syriac Manuscripts in the British Museum, Acquired since the year 1838*, 3 vols. (London: Trustees of the British Museum, 1870–1872).